

ANMED

News Bulletin on Archaeology
from Mediterranean Anatolia

22 2024

ISSN 2636-8218

ANMED

News Bulletin on Archaeology from Mediterranean Anatolia
22 2024

<i>Mode of publication</i>	Worldwide e-journal
<i>Publisher certificate number</i>	18318
<i>ISSN</i>	2636-8218
<i>Publisher management</i>	Koç Üniversitesi Rumelifeneri Yolu, 34450 Sarıyer / İstanbul
<i>Publisher</i>	Metin Sitti, President, on behalf of Koç Üniversitesi
<i>Editor-in-chief</i>	Oğuz Tekin
<i>Editorial Board</i>	Prof. Dr. Engin Akyürek (Koç Üniversitesi) Prof. Dr. Sencan Altınoluk (Çanakkale Onsekiz Mart Üniversitesi) Assoc. Prof. Dr. Aliye Erol (İstanbul Üniversitesi) Assoc. Prof. Dr. Hüseyin Köker (Süleyman Demirel Üniversitesi) Prof. Dr. Fatih Onur (Akdeniz Üniversitesi) Assoc. Prof. Dr. Rana Özbal (Koç Üniversitesi) Prof. Dr. Inge Uytterhoeven (Koç Üniversitesi)
<i>Editor of this issue</i>	Oğuz Tekin
©	Koç Üniversitesi AKMED (Suna & İnan Kırac Research Center for Mediterranean Civilizations) Articles submitted to the journal are published after undergoing the peer review process.
<i>Production</i>	Zero Production Ltd. Abdullah Sok. No. 17 Taksim 34433 İstanbul Tel: +90 (212) 244 75 21 • Fax: +90 (212) 244 32 09 info@zerobooksonline.com ; www.zerobooksonline.com
<i>Mailing address</i>	Koç Üniversitesi AKMED (Suna & İnan Kırac Akdeniz Medeniyetleri Araştırma Merkezi) Barbaros Mah. Kocatepe Sok. No. 22 Kaleiçi 07100 Antalya - Türkiye Tel: +90 (242) 243 42 74 • Fax: +90 (242) 243 80 13 https://akmed.ku.edu.tr akmed@ku.edu.tr

KOÇ ÜNİVERSİTESİ

AKMED

KOÇ UNIVERSITY

Suna & İnan Kırac

Research Center for

Mediterranean Civilizations

AKMED

KOÇ UNIVERSITY

Suna & İnan Kırac

Research Center for

Mediterranean Civilizations

22 2024

ANMED

News Bulletin on Archaeology
from Mediterranean Anatolia

Contents

Towards a New Publication Process	Oğuz TEKİN	v
Byzantine Seals and Stamps from the Troy Museum	Sencan ALTINOLUK	1
A New Coin Type of Seleucia (Silifke)	Remziye BOYRAZ SEYHAN	6
An Iao Amulet from Antioch	Aliye EROL	10
Unpublished Early Byzantine Bronze Balance Weights with Unit Marks in the Pera Museum	Yavuz Selim GÜLER	14
Three Six-Libra Lead Weights from Ionia	Oğuz TEKİN	18
Küçükçekmece Lake Basin (Bathonea*) Excavations 2023 Coin Finds	Arif YACI	23
REPORTS		
Anemurium Excavation 2023 Works <i>Anemurium Kazısı 2023 Yılı Çalışmaları</i>	Mehmet TEKOCAK Cihangir ALDEMİR	33
2023 Elaiussa Sebaste Excavation Works <i>Elaiussa Sebaste Kazısı 2023 Çalışmaları</i>	H. Asena KIZILARSLANOĞLU	38
Lyrbe (?) Archaeological Survey - 2023 <i>Lyrbe (?) Yüzey Araştırması 2023 Yılı Çalışmaları</i>	Işıl R. IŞIKLIKAYA LAUBSCHER Selma BULGURLU GÜN	42
Unique Floor Mosaic Discovered in Olympos 2023 Excavation <i>Olympos 2023 Yılı Çalışmalarında Tespit Edilen Ünik Bir Zemin Mozaiği</i>	Gökçen Kurtuluş ÖZTAŞKIN Muradiye BURSALI	47

A New Coin Type of Seleucia (Silifke)

Remziye BOYRAZ SEYHAN

Abstract

This article introduces a new coin type minted in the ancient city of Seleucia ad Calycadnum, located in the Cilicia Tracheia. Although the coin lacks an ethnic identifier, its attribution to the city is based on elements present in the city's autonomous coinage, featuring the club of Heracles on the obverse and a flower on the reverse. This discovery contributes a new type to the autonomous coin series of the Hellenistic period from this city.

Keywords: Numismatic, Cilician coinage, Seleucia ad Calycadnum, civic coins, Heracles' club

The ancient city of Seleucia (Σελεύκεια ἐν τῷ Καλυκάδνῳ, Seleucia ad Calycadnum, 'Seleukeia on the banks of the Kalykadnos'), one of the most important cities of Cilicia Tracheia and located in the present-day Silifke district of Mersin province, was founded in the Hellenistic Period and has survived as an important city and settlement throughout history.

The minting of the coins of the city started in the Hellenistic Period and continued intermittently in the Roman Imperial Period, ending with the reign of Gallienus (253-260 AD).¹ It is known that there was a royal mint in Seleucia during the Seleucid Period. The earliest examples of Seleucid coins minted in the city are the tetradrachms² minted during the reigns of Seleucus III (226-223 BC) and Antiochus III (197-189 BC)³ and the latest examples are from the time of Seleucus⁴ VI (ca. 98-94 BC?).⁵

1 For evaluations of the coins of Seleucia, see Nicolet 1971; Nicolet 1979; Cox 1941; Head 1911; Imhoof-Blumer 1890, 712-14; Imhoof-Blumer 1902, 481-86.

2 SC I, 916 (<https://numismatics.org/sco/id/sc.1.916>).

3 SC I.1, 386, nr. 1016.

4 Houghton 1989, 98.

5 Houghton 1989, 78; Cohen 1995, 369; for a summary of Seleucid mints in the city see Boyraz Seyhan 2021, 141 ff.

The earliest autonomous coins of Seleucia date to the 2nd/1st century BC. They bear the legend ΣΕΛΕΥΚΕΩΝ, its abbreviated form, or ΣΕΛΕΥΚΕΩΝ ΤΩΝ ΠΡΟΣ ΤΩΙ ΚΑΛΥΚΑΔΝΩΙ.⁶ It is generally accepted that the autonomous coins of the city in this group were minted after 169/8 BC, probably during the reign of Antiochus IV (175-164 BC).⁷

The symbols seen on Seleucid royal mints are the elements that provide the strongest connection with the autonomous coins of the city.⁸ The most striking symbols on the Seleucid royal coins, three symbols which numismatists suggest attribution to Seleucia, -the owl⁹, horse protome¹⁰ and flower¹¹- draw attention. These symbols were later used on Hellenistic and Roman imperial coins, sometimes on the obverse and sometimes on the reverse, in various series, sometimes as the main type and sometimes as symbols.

6 Cohen 1995, 369; MacKay 1968, 90 ff.; Sayar 2004, 22.

7 Houghton 1989, 83; Head (1911, 715) states that the city started minting coins in the 2nd century BC and suggests their early minting [Type H3] as Aphrodite/Flower.

8 Houghton (1989, 79), who has analyzed the coins of Cilicia, notes in a short table that almost without exception, after the reign of Antiochus III, cities expressed themselves with symbols or reverse types on the royal coins minted. He notes that Tarsus used Heracles' club and wings, Mopsus the fire altar, and Soli the head of Athena, a bunch of grapes and an owl.

9 Houghton 1989, 91, nr. 31.

10 A small-scale coin mint related to the campaign of Seleucus III was attributed to Seleucia by Newell (1941, 235) because of the horse protome it bears. On the other hand, Houghton suggested that the flower symbol seen on the coins of the city from Antiochus III to Seleucus VI should be attributed to Seleucia due to its continuity, but the horse protome calls into question the attribution to Seleucia, Meadows 2009, 72; see also SC I.1, 386 ff.

11 Houghton 1989, 79, 80-82.

In our study on the coins of Seleucia,¹² it has been determined that the autonomous coins from the Hellenistic Period show three distinct characteristics.¹³

1. Coins with the full city ethnic: These are categorized in our study as group H1 (Athena/Nike) and group H2 (Apollo/horse protome). The connection between these coins is clear; the first group is a largest denomination, while the second represents smaller one. They bear the first two to three letters or monograms of the city's official' names on the obverse, and full ethnic on the reverse, and the monograms/abbreviations or the first two to three letters of the names of two or three magistrates responsible for minting the coins in the blank.¹⁴ These coins are sometimes similar to the royal issues in terms of monograms.¹⁵
2. Coins without city ethnic: These coins sometimes have monograms or letters, but lack a city ethnic, so they may be dated earlier than Group 1, but they are similar to both Group 1 and Group 3 in terms of types or monograms.
3. Coins bearing only short city ethnic and magistrate' names: These are the heaviest and largest in diameter among the city's issues. However, the number of surviving examples is quite limited compared to the other groups.

This article will introduce a new coin type of the city that has not been recorded so far in the existing catalogs and collections (fig. 1). This coin is in the collection of the Silifke Museum (museum inv.no. 8263).¹⁶ The obverse shows the club of Heracles within a dotted border; this side of the coin is worn, so the ethnic or legend is unclear. The reverse depicts a five-petaled flower within a dotted border. There is no ethnic, an illegible letter (S?) in the field to the left of the flower, and the letter "N" in the field to the right.

¹² For more detailed information, see Boyraz Seyhan 2021.

¹³ For Head's assessment, see Head 1911, 727.

¹⁴ Letters such as ΣΑ and ΝΚ indicate workshops and it is thought that these were mobile workshops. For detailed information see Mørkholm 1964, 57; Houghton 1989.

¹⁵ These mint marks can also be detected on the coins of Elaiussa Sebaste (Houghton 1989, 81) and Tarsus (Houghton 1989, 82-83).

¹⁶ The ancient coins of the Silifke Museum are being prepared for publication by Prof. Dr. Oğuz Tekin, and it was with his kind permission that I included the coins of Seleucia in the museum collection in my doctoral study. I would like to sincerely thank him for allowing me to publish this unic coin here, and for his suggestions and corrections regarding the text.

FIG. 1a-b 2nd-1st century BC. Obv.: Heracles' club, dotted border; Rev.: Flower, dotted border, AE 13 mm, 2.33 g, 12h, Silifke Museum, inv. no. 8263.

The club of Heracles on the obverse is also seen, though less frequently, on a coin type of Seleucia that can be dated to a later period. This coin type features an owl on the obverse and Heracles' club on the reverse (fig. 2).

FIG. 2 1st century BC - Roman Imperial Period. Obv.:¹⁷ Owl, left, head frontal, within a wreath, ΔΙΟΚΚΟΥΡΗ[ΔΟΥ]; Rev.: Heracles' club, dotted border, CEΛΕΥΚΕ[ΩΝ]. AE 15 mm, 2.51 g. Pecunem | Naumann, Auction 20, 3 Aug 2014, 355.

Although the club attributed to Heracles, may point to connection between the demi-god and the city, no substantial evidence indicating his connection with the city has been found. From an iconographic point of view, Heracles' club was used extensively on the coins of the Macedonian kingdom, as he was the mythological ancestor of the kings of Macedonia.¹⁸ Heracles' club was used on the coins of the Seleucid kings -Antiochus III and Demetrius I-, as well as on the coins of Tyre (Ty or Sour, Lebanon) as the main coin type of the city.¹⁹ It is also seen as a symbol on the coins of Lysimachus.²⁰

It is known that Heracles was one of the most important cults in the neighboring city of Tarsus. The local coins of Tarsus dated to the reign of Mazaeus (ca. 327 BC) have an ear of wheat on the obverse and Heracles' club on the reverse in the blank, which is also the symbol

¹⁷ This type shows confusion in various sources regarding the identification of the obverse and reverse.

¹⁸ Mørkholm 2000, 47.

¹⁹ Mørkholm 1964, 53.

²⁰ Lysimachos, AR, Tetradrachm, Chios, ca. 235 BC <https://www.coinarchives.com/a/openlink.php?l=7850961464|258|57bfe94ce295c9554102f8bf0a9362ec>

of the local god Sandan, who was syncretized with Heracles by the Greeks.²¹ In addition, the coins of the city dated between 164-30 BC show Heracles' club in a wreath on the obverse and Zeus seated on a throne on the reverse.²² Although there are debates about the dating of these coins, they are dated to a wide range of periods from the third quarter of the 3rd century BC to 60/50 BC.²³

The club of Heracles is also found on the coins of Nagidus, a city of Cilicia Trachea.²⁴ It is also accepted among the symbols of the Priest-Kingdom of Olba, and located near Seleucia.²⁵ Therefore, it is not surprising to find this symbol on the coins of the city.

FIG. 3 Obv.: Head of a woman (Aphrodite?), right, A (or monogram?) in right field; Rev.: Flower, Δ and Λ. AE 13 mm, 1.60 g. CNG, EA 240, 8 Sep 2010, 228.

The flower on the reverse has also been employed on other coins of the city as a symbol identified with the city. However, the flower represented on this coin is different from the flowers depicted on other types. The receptacle of the flower is depicted fuller and wider. However, it can also be seen that there are many variations of the flower depiction on coins. A similar example of the flower depicted on the coin can be seen on a coin (AE 1.60 g, 13 mm) with a female head (Aphrodite?)

21 BMC Lycaonia, 173, no. 65, pl. 31.7; Mørkholm 2000, 50; detailed description of Sandan depicted on Tarsus coins for his assessment, see Tekin 2021, 97-108; Goldman 1949, 174.

22 SNG France 2, nos. 1354-1372 and BMC Lycaonia, 183, nos. 125-26, pl. 33.8: In these catalogs the description of the obverse and reverse sides is recorded in reverse.

23 Meyer 2001, 505-18, abstract p. 509.

24 Tekin 2007, 369-90.

25 Heracles' club on the obverse, sickle on the reverse (41-69 BC), SNG Switzerland I Levante-Cilicia, no. 644; Heracles' club on the obverse (Hadrian period), BMC Lycaonia, 124, no. 21, pl. 22.8. The Priest-Kingdom of Olba is known to have been an active power in the region between the Lamus and Calycadnus rivers in the 2nd-1st centuries BC, Sayar 2016, 108 and 113.

on the obverse and a flower on the reverse.²⁶ This coin is also very similar in dimension (AE 13 mm, 2.33 g) (fig. 3).

We can therefore suggest that the coin can easily be attributed to Seleucia, adding a new type to the city's autonomous coinage. The coin in question demonstrates continuity in Seleucian coinage traditions through its employment of symbols that were previously featured on the city's minted issues. These same symbols appear again throughout the Hellenistic and Roman imperial periods. By introducing a new type among the city's minor denominated coin types, this single specimen curiosity as to whether similar examples may emerge in other collections going forward. Its classification contributes to further illuminate Seleucia's monetary programmes and iconography during the 2nd-1st centuries BC.

Bibliography

BMC Lycaonia. Hill, G.F. 1981. *Catalogue of the Greek Coins of Lycaonia, Isauria and Cilicia* (reprinted) Sala Bolognese, Arnaldo Forni.

Boyraz Seyhan, R. 2021. "Seleukeia (Silifke): Tarihi ve Sikkeleri." PhD thesis, İstanbul Üniversitesi.

Cohen, G.M. 1995. *The Hellenistic Settlements in Europe, the Islands, and Asia Minor*. Berkeley: University of California Press.

Cox, D.H. 1941. *A Tarsus Coin Collection in the Adana Museum*, Series Numismatic Notes and Monographs. New York: American Numismatic Society. <http://numismatics.org/digitalibrary/ark:/53695/nnan133090>.

Goldman, H. 1949. "Sandon and Herakles." *Commemorative Studies in Honor of Theodore Leslie Shear*, Hesperia Supplements, Vol. 8:164-174+454.

Head, B.V. 1911. *Historia Numorum. A Manual of Greek Numismatics* (New and Enlarged edition). Oxford: Clarendon Press.

Houghton, A. 1989. "The Royal Seleucid Mint of Seleucia on the Calycadnus." In *Kraay-Mørkholm Essays. Numismatic studies in memory of C.M. Kraay and O. Mørkholm*, G. Le Rider et al., eds., 77-98. Louvain.

Imhoof-Blumer, F. 1890. *Griechische Münzen: Neue Beiträge und Untersuchungen*. München: Verlag der k. Akad. bemie.

Imhoof-Blumer, F. 1902. *Kleinasiatische Münzen II*. Wien: Alfred Hölder.

26 Boyraz Seyhan 2021, Type H3.5 No. 17; Tahberer 2014, 1158.

- MacKay, Th. 1968. "Olba in Rough Cilicia." PhD thesis, Bryn Mawr College.
- Meadows, A. 2009. "The Eras of Pamphylia and Seleucid Invasions of Asia Minor." *AJN Second Series* 21:51-88.
- Meyer, M. 2001. "Cilicia as Part of the Seleucid Empire – The Beginning of Municipal Coinage. La Cilicie." *Espaces et pouvoirs locaux (Ie millénaire av. J.-C. – Ie siècle ap. J.-C.)*, Actes de la Table Ronde d'Istanbul, 2-5.
- Mørkholm, O. 1964. "Seleucid Coins from Cilicia ca. 220-150 B.C." *ANSMS* 11:53-62.
- Mørkholm, O. 2000. *Erken Hellenistik Çağ Sikkeleri. Büyük İskender'in Tahta Çıkışından Apameia Barışı'na Kadar (İ.Ö. 336-188)*, Çev. O. Tekin. İstanbul: Homer Kitabevi.
- Newell, E. T. 1941. *The Coinage of the Western Seleucid Mints from Seleucus I to Antiochus III*, *Numismatic Studies*, No. 4, New York, American Numismatic Society (WSM).
- Nicolet, H. 1971. "Monnaies de Bronze de Cilicie (Séleucie du Kalykadnos)." *RN* 13 (6e):26-37.
- Nicolet, H. 1979. "Bronzes de Séleucie du Kalykadnos (Cilicia)." *BSFN* 97, no. 8:287-88.
- Sayar, M.H. 2004. "Das Ebene Kilikien vom Tod Alexanders des Grossen bis zur Gründung der Provinz Cilicia durch Kaiser Vespasian (323 v. Chr.-71/73 n. Chr.)." *Kulturbegrenzung in einem Brückenland. Gottheiten und Kulte als Indikatoren von Akkulturationsprozessen im Ebenen Kilikien*, AMS 53, Ed. K. Ehling et al., 17-28.
- Sayar, M.H. 2016. "Olba: Tapınak Devleti'nden Şehir Devletine." *Seleucia* 6:107-118.
- SC I. Houghton, A., C. Lorber, and O. Hoover, *Seleucid Coins. A Comprehensive Catalogue*, New York: The American Numismatic Society, 2002-2008.
- SNG France 2. *Sylloge Nummorum Graecorum France 2 Cabinet des Médailles Cilicia*, Bibliothèque Nationale Numismatica Ars Classica, Paris, 1993.
- SNG Switzerland I Levante-Cilicia. *Sylloge Nummorum Graecorum Switzerland I, Levante-Cilicia*. Berne: Credit Suisse, E. Levante, 1986.
- Tahberer, B. 2014. *B. Tahberer Birikimi Antik Kilikia Sikkeleri Derlemesi: Ancient Cilician Coins from the Collection of B. Tahberer*, Vancouver.
- Tekin, O. 2007. "Sikkeler." In *Nagidos: Dağlık Kilikia'da Bir Antik Kent Kazısının Sonuçları*, edited by S. Durugönül, 369-90. İstanbul: Suna – İnan Kıraç Akdeniz Medeniyetleri Araştırma Merkezi.
- Tekin, O. 2021. "Sandan on the Coins of Tarsus in Cilicia." *Traditions through Empires. Cities of Asia Minor and their Coin Images*, AMS, edited by S. Kerschbaum, and H. Vidin, 97-108.
- Makale Geliş / Received : 03.06.2024
Makale Kabul / Accepted : 26.07.2024
- BOYRAZ SEYHAN, Remziye, Dr.
Koç Üniversitesi AKMED
Barbaros Mah. Kocatepe Sok. No: 22
07100, Kaleiçi - Antalya
rboyraz@ku.edu.tr
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5194-8833>

